

Analysis of financial performance by ratio analysis method: An application in air transport sector in Turkey

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <p>Keywords: Financial Performance Ratio Analysis Air Transport Sector</p> <p>Received: 16 September 2024 Revised: 7 December 2024 Accepted: 10 December 2024</p>	<p>This study examines the impact of the Coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic on the financial performance of Turkey's major airline companies, including Turkish Airlines and Pegasus Airlines. The ratio analysis, based on data from 2018 to 2023, demonstrates the alterations in the airline industry and the financial implications of these changes. The findings of the research demonstrate that the pandemic has had a detrimental impact on the revenue, cost, and profitability ratios of airline companies. In particular, the decline in the number of passengers and the increased operating costs have had a markedly adverse effect on the financial performance of the companies. Furthermore, the findings demonstrate that the robust financial position of Turkish Airlines prior to the pandemic enabled it to demonstrate greater resilience during the crisis, although it still incurred substantial losses. In contrast, Pegasus Airlines exhibited a more resilient financial structure, enabling it to navigate the crisis with less damage. Consequently, this study offers valuable insights into the post-Covid-19 recovery trajectory of the airline industry and proposes avenues for future research.</p>

1. Introduction

Over the past two decades, the air transport industry has been confronted with a series of significant challenges and crises. Among these crises, events such as the terrorist attacks of 11 September 2001, the outbreak of SARS in 2003, and the global economic crisis of 2008-2009, as well as the H1N1 influenza pandemic, have had a significant impact on the industry. The MERS outbreak in 2012 and the subsequent pandemic that broke out in late 2019, along with the 2009 outbreak of Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), have had varying degrees of negative impact on the industry (ICAO, 2021). The Coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic represents one of the most significant crises to impact the air transport industry. In response to the pandemic, airline operators have implemented a series of measures, including reducing or halting flight operations, cancelling or postponing aircraft orders, removing high-cost aircraft from the fleet, downsizing fleets, narrowing flight networks, modifying aircraft configurations, diversifying into cargo transportation, and reducing staffing levels. These measures have had a detrimental impact on the financial and operational activities of airline companies (Albers & Rundshagen, 2020). The restrictions imposed by the ongoing pandemic have led to a notable decline in the willingness of individuals to travel by air, as evidenced by a reduction in the number of passengers using airlines. This has resulted in significant financial and

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Cite this article: Akçay, Ş., Asker, V. (2024). Analysis of financial performance by ratio analysis method: An application in air transport sector in Turkey. *Research in Aviation Management*, 4(1), 11-23. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14503569>

operational challenges for numerous airlines, with many struggling to maintain operational viability and facing the potential risk of bankruptcy. This decline in demand has manifested itself in a significant reduction in passenger numbers, with a 60 % decrease in 2020 and a 49% decrease in 2021 compared to 2019. Similarly, the total losses incurred by the air transport sector exceeded USD 372 million in 2020 and reached USD 324 million in 2021 (ICAO, 2021). During the period of the global pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, a number of airlines, including Flybe and Alitalia, encountered financial difficulties, with some ultimately going bankrupt, as did Latam Airlines. Conversely, some airlines, including Lufthansa and Air France-KLM, were able to maintain their operations through the provision of government subsidies (Abate, Purwanto, & Christidis, 2020). The adverse effects of the Coronavirus pandemic have had a detrimental impact on both traditional airlines and those that have adopted a low-budget business strategy. The liberalisation of the air transport industry in the United States in the late 1970s led to the emergence of the low-cost business model, which is based on offering tickets to customers at a lower price by reducing the services provided during the flight process. This approach has been adopted by airline companies in other countries with remarkable swiftness (Malighetti, Paleari, & Redondi, 2009).

The financial performance of airline companies is contingent upon the decisions made by their managerial personnel. In periods of economic turbulence, such as the global pandemic of 2020, the decisions made by management can have a significant impact on the resilience and recovery of a company. The advent of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic has prompted airline companies to devise and implement a range of operational strategies. In this context, airline companies have sought to navigate the crisis through the implementation of diverse operational and financial measures (Asker, 2023). This study aims to examine the effects of the Coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19) outbreak on the financial performance of airline companies, including Turkish Airlines and Pegasus Airlines, using a ratio analysis method and to evaluate the results obtained comparatively. The following sections present a review of the literature, followed by a detailed discussion of ratio analysis. Thereafter, the findings of the analysis are analysed and evaluated. The final section presents a synthesis of the results of the analysis and suggestions for future studies.

2. Literature Review

A substantial body of literature exists which analyses the financial and operational performance of companies both before and after the advent of the global pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, commonly known as the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19). To illustrate, Koçyiğit (2009) assessed the performance of 14 airline companies that are members of the Star Alliance alliance during the 2005-2007 period, utilising Tobin's q ratio and other financial indicators. The findings of the study indicated that the majority of enterprises exhibited a low Tobin's q ratio. Additionally, it was observed that the performance of companies in the Asia-Pacific region was comparatively more favourable than that of companies in other regions.

Öncü et al. (2013) conducted a study to evaluate the efficiency of airline passenger transport enterprises. The study employed the data envelopment analysis technique to examine the effective utilisation of resources by these enterprises. The analysis yielded three effective enterprises out of seven. Additionally, potential avenues for improvement were identified for enterprises exhibiting suboptimal efficiency.

Kızıl and Aslan (2019) conducted a financial analysis of Turkish Airlines A.Ş. and Pegasus Airlines A.Ş. between 2013 and 2017, employing ratio analysis. In the course of the research, a total of 17 different financial ratios were calculated using the data obtained from the financial statements of both airline companies. The financial information obtained from the PDP was employed in the analysis, with the application carried out using the Microsoft Excel programme. The findings indicate that Pegasus Airlines A.Ş. exhibits superior liquidity ratios in comparison to Turkish Airlines A.Ş. Furthermore, it was noted that Pegasus demonstrated superior performance in terms of net working capital and debt repayment capacity. Both companies exhibited operational efficiency, with fluctuating profit margins. Consequently, Pegasus Airlines A.Ş. exhibited enhanced financial performance compared to Turkish Airlines A.Ş., with a more favourable position in terms of investability.

Pehlivanlı (2020) examined the impact of the global pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus on the Turkish aviation sector. He employed Data Envelopment Analysis and Malmquist-TFP Index techniques to assess the

efficiency and effectiveness of airports in the first quarter of 2019 and 2020. The results of the study indicated that nine out of the twenty airports were efficient prior to the onset of the pandemic, while ten airports demonstrated efficiency in the post-pandemic period.

Keleş and Özulucan (2020) employed ratio analysis to examine the financial performance of airline companies operating in the aviation sector. In this study, the most recent annual financial statements of Turkish Airlines A.Ş. and Pegasus Airlines A.Ş., both listed on Borsa Istanbul and announced on the Public Disclosure Platform (KAP), were utilized. The analysis evaluated the financial position of both companies based on liquidity, financial structure, operating and profitability ratios. The results demonstrate that the financial performance of Pegasus Airlines A.Ş. outperforms that of Turkish Airlines A.Ş., rendering it a more attractive option for investors. Pegasus' superior liquidity and profitability ratios contribute to its stronger performance. These findings suggest that investors should consider Pegasus Airlines as a more reliable choice in their decisions.

Kiracı and Asker (2021) conducted a comprehensive analysis of the impact of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic on the airline industry. In the course of their investigation, the researchers employed a data set comprising quarterly observations from the 2018 to 2020 period. To elucidate the multifaceted impact of the pandemic, they employed a CRITIC-based EDAS and Trend Analysis approach. Their findings revealed that the pandemic exerted a pronounced influence on airline performance, with some airlines demonstrating superior resilience in navigating the challenges posed by the pandemic.

Dağlı (2021) employed the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to an Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) method to evaluate the financial performance of leading European airlines prior to and during the period of the global pandemic caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), commonly known as the novel coronavirus. The financial performance of these airlines was then compared in the second quarter of 2019 and 2020. The analysis yielded the following rankings for the second quarter of 2019: Pegasus in first place, IAG in second, and AFL Airlines in third. For the second quarter of 2020, the rankings were NAX in first, Pegasus in second, and Turkish Airlines in third.

Asker (2021) conducted an analysis of the financial performance of a total of 31 airlines, which are members of international airline alliances such as Star Alliance, SkyTeam and Oneworld, between 2016 and 2019. This analysis employed the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) technique and aimed to compare the efficiency values of airline strategic alliances within themselves. The results of the analysis indicate that the efficiency of all airline strategic alliances increased during the period between 2016 and 2017, but subsequently decreased during the subsequent period between 2017 and 2018. During the 2018-2019 period, the decline in efficiency observed in the Star Alliance group persisted, whereas the Oneworld and SkyTeam groups exhibited a reversal of this trend, with an increase in efficiency. Conversely, six airlines in the Star Alliance group and a number of other airlines, including those in the SkyTeam and Oneworld groups, demonstrated consistently high levels of activity throughout the entire period under review. In contrast, six airlines in the Star Alliance group and three airlines in the SkyTeam and Oneworld groups were identified as exhibiting persistent inefficiency over the entire period.

Beyazgül et al. (2022) conducted a comprehensive analysis of the impact of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic on the financial stability of the land, sea, and air passenger transportation sectors in Turkey. In this context, the liquidity risks of the land, sea and air passenger transport sectors for 2019 and 2020 were analysed using the sectoral balance sheets provided by the CBRT. The financial failure risks of the sectors were assessed using nine different financial ratios and various models, including Altman Z, Altman Z', Altman Z'', Fulmer H and Ohlson. The findings indicate that all three sectors exhibit elevated levels of liquidity and financial failure risks. Notably, the airline passenger transport sector witnessed a pronounced surge in these risks during the pandemic, when compared to the pre-pandemic period. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that the airline passenger transport sector was the most significantly impacted by the pandemic.

Asker (2022), the financial efficiency and productivity changes of 24 airlines adopting traditional and low-cost business models were examined over the period 2016-2019. The Malmquist Total Factor Productivity Index (MTFP) method was used to analyse the data. Furthermore, the financial performance of these airlines was evaluated both prior to and following the advent of the global pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. The research findings indicate that the technical efficiency and technological development values of traditional airlines increased during the 2016-2017 and 2018-2019 periods. However, the improvement in total factor

productivity was observed only during the 2016-2018 period. While the technical and technological efficiency values of low-cost airlines increased in the 2016-2017 and 2017-2018 periods, total factor productivity remained constant only in the 2017-2018 period.

Koç (2022) examined the effects of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic on the financial profitability and leasing transactions of airline companies such as Turkish Airlines and Lufthansa, which are subject to the Turkish Financial Reporting Standards. The findings of the study indicated a notable decline in the profitability of both Lufthansa and Turkish Airlines. Between 2019 and 2020, a substantial reduction in total sales revenues was observed. These outcomes substantiate the assertion that the pandemic exerted a detrimental impact on the financial performance of airline businesses.

Keleş (2023) evaluated the success of Europe's nine largest traditional airlines before and after the pandemic as of 2020 by employing the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method. The study employed a comparative approach to assess the efficiency levels of these airlines before and after the pandemic period, utilising aviation data from 2019 to 2020. The analysis considered three inputs, namely 'seat kilometres supplied', 'number of employees' and 'number of aircraft', and one output, 'number of passengers'. The results demonstrated that Aegean Airlines exhibited optimal efficiency throughout the pre- and post-pandemic periods.

Irmak and Pelit (2023) examined the effects of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic on airline businesses in Turkey and worldwide. The results of the research demonstrated that the airline transport sector was adversely affected by a decline in passenger demand and passenger traffic during the pandemic.

Rençber (2024) was to examine the performance of Turkish Airlines in the Borsa Istanbul Sustainability Index from economic, social and environmental perspectives. Entropy and TOPSIS methods were employed in the analyses using data for the period 2014-2022. The results demonstrated that the negative effects of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic on the aviation sector are considerable.

3. Ratio Analysis

Ratios are financial indicators that demonstrate the relationship between two related items within an arithmetic expression. These items reflect the various elements that comprise the financial position of the enterprise (Orak, 2015). The calculation of simple mathematical relationships between items in financial statements, otherwise known as ratios, is not an objective in itself. It is crucial to analyse and interpret these ratios. Ratios should be employed and evaluated in order to respond to meaningful questions about the business, thus rendering them a useful analytical tool (Kiran, 2013). For those engaged in financial management, ratio analysis represents an invaluable tool for understanding and analysing the effects of business activities, and plays a significant role in the planning of future financing needs. Financial managers frequently employ ratio analysis to analyse raw data in financial statements. In essence, financial ratios are the results obtained by dividing one financial figure by another financial figure. While each ratio is relatively straightforward to calculate, each ratio should be subjected to careful analysis in order to accurately measure the firm's performance (Kiran, 2013).

In the evaluation phase of the ratio analysis method, it is necessary to determine the ratios obtained from the financial statements with ratios reflecting the actual situation of the enterprise and to interpret these ratios logically in line with the objectives of the analysis. In the interpretation process, comparisons with generally accepted ratios, with enterprises and companies in the relevant sector, and with the previous period data of the enterprise will help to obtain healthier results (Yenisu, 2019). The methods used in ratio analysis are liquidity, leverage, activity, profitability and stock market performance ratios (Saraç, 2012).

3.1. Liquidity Ratios

Liquidity is the speed and ease with which a good can be converted into cash (Akdoğan & Tenker, 2010). Liquidity ratios are used to assess a firm's ability to pay its short-term debts and to determine the adequacy of operating resources (Akgüç, Financial Management, 2010).

Liquidity ratios are divided into three: Current Ratio, Liquidity Ratio and Cash Ratio.

3.1.1. Current Ratio

The current ratio provides insight into an entity's capacity to meet its short-term liabilities and assesses the adequacy of net working capital.

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

While this ratio is generally expected to be around 2, it is known that 1.5 is considered sufficient in developing countries (Yenisu, 2019). A high level of this ratio indicates that the enterprise in question has a strong capacity to repay its debts. However, an excessively high current ratio indicates that there are excess unused funds in the enterprise and that resources are not used efficiently (Çabuk & Lazol, 2010).

3.1.2. Cash Ratio

In order to evaluate the entity's short-term liquidity position, it is necessary to compare the sum of its cash and marketable securities with that of its short-term liabilities. This comparison is made using a ratio known as the cash ratio (Sariaslan & Erol, 2008).

$$\text{Cash Ratio} = \frac{\text{Cash and Cash Equivalents}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

It is generally advisable that the cash ratio should not fall below 0.20, as this may indicate a potential risk to the business's liquidity, which may in turn increase the need for the business to apply for new loans. Nevertheless, an excessively high cash ratio is also inadvisable. A persistent cash surplus within the enterprise may be indicative of inefficacious monetary utilisation, which may constrain the enterprise's potential for growth and efficiency (Akdoğan & Tenker, 2010).

3.2. Financial Structure Ratios

The ratios employed during financial structure analysis furnish crucial insight into an enterprise's capacity to honour its obligations in the event of operational losses, asset depreciation or unrealised projected cash flows (Akgüç, 2011).

Among the various financial structure ratios, there are several key indicators, including the financial leverage ratio, the equity to total assets ratio, the financing ratio and the short-term liabilities to total resources ratio (Akgüç, Financial Statement Analysis, 2011).

3.2.1 Financial Leverage Ratio

This ratio indicates the extent to which an entity's assets are financed through debt, and is commonly designated as the leverage ratio. It is calculated by dividing total debts by total assets (Çabuk & Lazol, 2010).

$$\text{Financial Leverage Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Liabilities}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

A high financial leverage ratio indicates that the risk margin for lenders decreases and the probability of the enterprise experiencing difficulties in interest and debt payments increases (Ercan & Ban, 2009).

3.2.2 Ratio of Equity to Total Assets

This ratio is calculated by dividing the amount of equity by the total assets (Yenisu, 2019).

$$\text{Ratio of Equity to Total Asset} = \frac{\text{Total Equity}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

The ratio of shareholders' equity to total assets provides insight into the extent to which the entity's assets are financed by the owners and shareholders. In other words, it determines the proportion of shareholders' equity in the context of general resources. This ratio reflects the long-term debt repayment capacity of the enterprise. A high ratio indicates that the company will not have any problems with its long-term debts and interest payments. It also indicates that the safety margin is sufficient for those who provide credit to the enterprise. An increase in this ratio over time is generally considered to be an indicator of successful management (Akdoğan & Tenker, 2010).

3.2.3. Financing Rate

The financing ratio is a measure of the financial autonomy of an enterprise. It is also referred to as the payment capacity coefficient or borrowing ratio. The ratio is calculated by dividing equity by total liabilities (Yenisu, 2019).

$$\text{Financing Rate} = \frac{\text{Total Equity}}{\text{Total Liabilities}}$$

It is recommended that the financing ratio is at least 1, as a high ratio allows the company to avoid the pressure of creditors. A ratio below 1 indicates that lenders have invested more than business owners. This undermines the confidence of creditors and may result in the inability to repay debts through the consumption of enterprise financial resources due to the high interest burden in periods of economic recession (Akdoğan & Tenker, 2010).

3.2.4. Ratio of Current Liabilities to Total Liabilities

This ratio indicates the extent to which the enterprise's economic assets are financed by short-term debt.

$$\frac{\text{Current Liabilities}}{\text{Total Liabilities}}$$

In Western countries, this ratio is typically regarded as a benchmark that should not exceed one-third in industrial enterprises. However, this ratio is observed to be at higher levels in Turkey, largely due to factors such as the underdevelopment of capital markets and the scarcity of institutions offering long-term loans. Additionally, the substantial proportion of current assets among the assets of enterprises and the prevalence of high inflation contribute to the overall elevation of this ratio (Akgüç, Financial Management, 2010).

3.2.5. Ratio of Long-Term Liabilities to Total Liabilities

This ratio indicates the extent to which the firm's long-term economic resources are financed by loans. An increase in the ratio suggests that the enterprise is reliant on long-term resources, which increases the interest burden and reduces the profit margin (Çetiner, 2010).

$$\frac{\text{Long Term Liabilities}}{\text{Total Liabilities}}$$

3.3. Activity Ratios (Turnover Rates)

Operating ratios represent a group of ratios that evaluate the effectiveness with which a company utilises its assets. These ratios are of particular importance, as they reveal the relationship between a company's sales and its assets (Sariaslan & Erol, 2008).

Turnover ratios may be classified into several categories, including receivables turnover, inventory turnover, current asset turnover, net working capital turnover, fixed asset turnover, equity turnover and asset turnover (Sariaslan & Erol, 2008).

3.3.1 Receivable Turnover Rate

In addition to cash sales, a company's receivables represent a significant source of cash flow. Consequently, financial analysts are keen to assess the collectability and liquidity of receivables in great detail. The receivables turnover rate, or the time taken for receivables to be converted into cash, is a crucial indicator of an entity's ability to collect its receivables and its liquidity (Akgüç, Financial Statement Analysis, 2011).

$$\text{Receivable Turnover Rate} = \frac{\text{Net Sales}}{\text{Average Total Receivable}}$$

In the aforementioned formula, the term "the amount of credit sales" may be employed in lieu of "net sales." The average trade receivables are calculated as the sum of the trade receivables at the beginning and end of the period, divided by two (Yenisu, 2019).

$$\text{Average Collection Period of Receivables} = \frac{\text{Beginning and End of the period Receivables}}{2}$$

A high receivables turnover rate is indicative of the enterprise's capacity to effectively collect its receivables (Yenisu, 2019).

3.3.2. Asset Turnover Ratio

The asset turnover ratio is an indicator that measures the capital intensity and efficiency of asset utilisation within a company. This ratio is one of the factors that determine the profitability of the business (Yenisu, 2019).

$$\text{Asset Turnover Rate} = \frac{\text{Net Sales}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

Companies with low asset turnover ratios are typically associated with elevated risk and diminished profitability. In other words, a high level of this ratio is generally regarded as favourable (Akgüç, Financial Statement Analysis, 2011).

3.4. Profitability Ratios

The most commonly used ratios for the assessment of profit-generating capacity are the return on equity (efficiency), gross profit ratio (margin), net profit ratio (margin) and total asset profitability ratio (efficiency) (Sariaslan & Erol, 2008). Profitability ratios can be divided into two main categories: those which demonstrate the relationship between profit and capital, and those which elucidate the relationship between profit and sales.

3.4.1. Return on Assets Ratio

One of the most frequently employed ratios for the assessment of an enterprise's profit margin is the profitability ratio, which is calculated based on the net profit and total assets. This ratio enables the determination of a firm's profitability trajectory over time (Yenisu, 2019).

$$ROA = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

The utilisation of this ratio, also designated as return on assets, may, on occasion, culminate in erroneous outcomes. Accordingly, the utilisation of an alternative measure, such as 'Earnings Before Interest and Taxes (EBIT)', may facilitate the generation of more accurate results (Akgüç, Financial Statement Analysis, 2011). Nevertheless, it is typically advantageous to attain a high profitability ratio, as it demonstrates the capacity of assets to generate profit or, in other words, the extent to which assets are effectively utilised (Yenisu, 2019).

3.4.2. Profit and Sales Relationship

It is a common practice among companies to seek a high profit margin, defined as a high share of profit from sales. The analysis of the interrelationships between different measures of profit and sales enables businesses to evaluate their financial statements with greater precision. The ratios that elucidate the relationship between profit and sales include the operating profit margin, gross profit margin, net profit margin, and operating expenses to net sales (Yenisu, 2019).

3.4.2.1 Operating Profit Margin

The operating margin is employed to ascertain the profitability of a business's core operations.

$$\text{Operating Profit Margin} = \frac{\text{Operating Profit}}{\text{Net Sales}}$$

A high operating profit margin is indicative of the profitability and efficiency of the enterprise's core activities. Conversely, a downward trend in this ratio suggests a decline in the aforementioned profitability and efficiency (Çabuk & Lazol, 2010).

3.4.2.2. Gross Profit Margin

The gross profit margin is calculated by dividing the company's gross sales profit (gross profit) by net sales. This ratio expresses the ratio of net sales to gross sales profit as a percentage (Yenisu, 2019).

$$\text{Gross Profit Margin} = \frac{\text{Gross Profit}}{\text{Net Sales}}$$

The gross profit margin provides data on the gross profitability level of the company. A high or increasing ratio is considered a positive indicator for the enterprise (Akdoğan & Tenker, 2010).

3.4.2.3. Net Profit Margin

The net profit margin is employed for the evaluation of the enterprise's sales profitability. In other words, this ratio demonstrates the profit generated by the enterprise from each TL 1 of net sales (Yenisu, 2019).

$$\text{Net Profit Margin} = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Net Sales}}$$

In practice, the term 'profit margin' is typically understood to refer to the net profit margin. A high level of this ratio is indicative of a favourable situation for the business (Ercan & Ban, 2009).

4. Application

This section of the study employs ratio analysis to examine the financial performance of Turkish Airlines (THY) and Pegasus Airlines, two prominent players in the Turkish air transport sector, over the 2018-2023 period. The financial data of these airlines was obtained from the Public Disclosure Platform (PDP). The research delves into the liquidity ratios, financial structure ratios, operating ratios, and profitability ratios of these airlines, offering insights into their financial standing and operational dynamics.

4.1. Liquidity Ratios

This section presents the liquidity ratios of the airlines for the period 2018-2023, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Liquidity Ratios of Airline Companies

Ratios	Turkish Airlines						Pegasus					
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Current Ratio	0.86	0,80	0,65	0,72	0,87	0,94	1,24	1,28	0,82	1	0,99	1,29
Cash Ratio	0.31	0,42	0,28	0,39	0,49	0,07	0,77	0,88	0,55	0,55	0,50	0,43

The data presented in this table has been prepared in accordance with the information made available on the Public Disclosure Platform (PDP).

Prior to the advent of the pandemic, Turkish Airlines (THY) exhibited ratios that were already below the industry standard. The impact of the pandemic has resulted in a further deterioration of these ratios. However, there are indications that a recovery may be underway in 2022 and 2023. In contrast, the cash ratio has exhibited considerable volatility in the wake of the pandemic, with a notable decline observed in 2023. Prior to the onset of the pandemic, Pegasus Airlines demonstrated a greater alignment with established liquidity ratios and exhibited a comparatively lesser impact from the pandemic. In 2023, current ratios recovered and became aligned with the standards. Conversely, the cash ratio experienced a decline following the pandemic, yet demonstrated a slight increase in 2023. Both airlines encountered liquidity challenges during the pandemic, yet demonstrated resilience in subsequent periods. Consequently, it can be posited that Pegasus Airlines' liquidity ratios are more stable in general.

4.2. Financial Structure Ratios

This section presents the financial structure ratios of the airlines for the period 2018-2023. The data is presented in Table 2 for reference.

Table 2: Financial Structure Ratios of Airline Companies

Ratios	Turkish Airlines						Pegasus					
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Financial Leverage Ratio	0,71	0,72	0,78	0,74	0,10	0,06	0,72	0,75	0,81	0,87	0,21	0,15
Ratio of Equity to Total Assets	0,28	0,28	0,21	0,25	0,31	0,43	0,27	0,25	0,18	0,12	0,18	0,27
Financing Rate	2,48	2,60	3,74	2,90	0,33	0,15	2,67	2,94	4,39	6,77	1,74	0,57
Ratio of Current Liabilities to Total Liabilities	0,25	0,24	0,25	0,25	0,26	0,25	0,26	0,23	0,22	0,23	0,21	0,03
Ratio of Long-Term Liabilities to Total Liabilities	0,35	0,48	0,67	0,48	0,42	0,30	0,46	0,52	0,59	0,63	0,59	0,11

The data presented in this table has been prepared in accordance with the information made available on the Public Disclosure Platform (PDP).

In the period preceding the advent of the global pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the financial structure of Turkish Airlines (THY) was typified by elevated borrowing rates and diminished equity ratios. During the period of the global pandemic caused by the novel coronavirus, Turkish Airlines (THY) saw an increase in its borrowing rates. However, there was subsequently a recovery in both its debt and equity ratios. This indicates that the company has implemented measures to enhance its debt management and financial structures. Similarly, Pegasus Airlines exhibited comparable levels of borrowing and low equity ratios prior to the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. The company's borrowing ratios increased significantly during the period of the global pandemic caused by the novel coronavirus, but debt and equity ratios subsequently recovered. It can be argued that Pegasus Airlines has attempted to enhance its financial structures in a comparable manner to THY. In general, both companies encountered significant financial challenges during the pandemic, but it is believed that they took crucial steps to improve their financial structures in the aftermath of this period. The decline in borrowing ratios and the growth in equity ratios can be seen as an indication of the companies' efforts to ensure long-term financial stability.

4.3 Activity Ratios

This section presents the activity rates of the airlines for the period 2018-2023, as illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3: Operating Ratios of Airline Companies

Ratios	Turkish Airlines						Pegasus					
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Receivable Turnover Rate	21	24,2	11,7	7,3	17,2	18,7	45,1	32,3	14,9	31,6	36,3	42,2
Average Collection Period of Receivables	17,3	15,0	30,9	49,5	21,1	19,4	8,1	11,3	24,4	11,5	10,0	8,6
Asset Turnover Ratio	0,57	0,51	0,25	0,27	0,53	0,48	0,60	0,5	0,17	0,20	0,44	0,34

The data presented in this table has been prepared in accordance with the information made available on the Public Disclosure Platform (PDP).

Turkish Airlines witnessed a notable deterioration in its operational ratios during the course of the global pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. However, indications of recovery were discernible in the post-

pandemic period. The receivables turnover rate and ratios have demonstrated a recovery, as has the asset turnover rate. Pegasus Airlines

Operating ratios declined during the pandemic period; however, a stronger recovery was observed in the post-pandemic period. Receivables turnover rates have recovered significantly, and asset turnover rates have also improved. It can be concluded that both companies took important steps to improve their operating ratios in the post-pandemic period and entered a recovery process. This situation can be interpreted as an effort by the companies to increase their operational efficiency and financial performance once more.

4.4. Profitability Ratios

This section presents the profitability ratios of the airlines for the period 2018-2023, as detailed in Table 4.

Table 4: Profitability Ratios of Airline Companies

Ratios	Turkish Airlines						Pegasus					
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Gross Profit Margin	0,21	0,17	0,06	0,22	0,24	0,23	0,15	0,24	-0,26	0,01	0,27	0,23
Operating Profit Margin	0,11	0,07	-0,03	0,15	0,15	0,14	0,09	0,19	-0,28	0,05	0,22	0,18
Net Profit Margin	0,06	0,06	-0,12	0,05	0,02	0,09	0,03	0,12	-0,41	0,03	0,16	0,29
Return on Assets Ratio	0,03	0,03	-0,03	0,01	0,01	0,04	0,03	0,06	-0,07	0,02	0,07	0,10

The data presented in this table has been prepared in accordance with the information made available on the Public Disclosure Platform (PDP).

Both airlines encountered considerable financial difficulties during the global pandemic, with some profitability ratios declining to negative values. However, notable enhancements were observed in the profitability ratios of both companies in 2021 and beyond. In the post-pandemic period, Pegasus Airlines demonstrated a more robust performance compared to Turkish Airlines, particularly in the net profit ratio.

This recovery in the post-pandemic period can be interpreted as a recovery from the effects of the pandemic and an increase in operational efficiency. The improvement in financial performance indicates that these airlines may follow a more sustainable growth path in the future.

5. Conclusion

This paper presents an analysis of the financial performance of airline companies in Turkey between 2018 and 2023. It provides an important overview of the challenges currently facing the aviation sector and the strategies adopted by airlines to cope with crises. The findings of the research demonstrate how airline companies in the sector respond to unforeseen circumstances, such as the global pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, and the subsequent financial impact on their operations. In particular, the global pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus has had a profound impact on the airline industry, placing significant strain on businesses. In response to the pandemic, airline companies implemented emergency measures, including reducing the number of flights, downsizing their fleets, reducing costs, and laying off employees. These measures resulted in an increase in liquidity and financial failure risks, thereby precipitating a period of significant difficulty for the sector. The multiplicity of factors influencing the financial performance of airlines and the inherent uncertainties within the industry underscore the critical considerations that companies must address when formulating their future strategies. It is therefore crucial for companies to possess both operational and financial flexibility, as well as the capacity to respond rapidly and effectively to crises. Moreover, it may be necessary for airlines to reassess and adapt their financial strategies in order to guarantee their long-term viability. Consequently, this study can serve as a valuable resource for gaining insight into the present circumstances of the airline industry, examining the shifts occurring within the sector,

and formulating prospective strategies. A comprehensive analysis of the effects on the financial performance of airlines can provide insights into the decision-making processes of stakeholders in the industry and contribute to the future development of the industry. In this study, liquidity, financial structure, activity, and profitability ratios were examined, and several key findings were identified. The following points emerged as particularly noteworthy:

A comparative analysis of the liquidity ratios of Pegasus Airlines and Turkish Airlines reveals that the former exhibits a higher degree of liquidity than the latter. This observation suggests that Pegasus Airlines possesses a superior capacity to meet its short-term financial obligations.

The examination of financial structure ratios further underscores the significance of maintaining optimal indebtedness ratios for strengthening financial structures. The elevated indebtedness ratios observed in Turkish Airlines highlight the imperative for vigilance in financial risk management.

In terms of operating ratios, it has been determined that both companies generally operate efficiently, although there are instances where performance is subject to fluctuations. This demonstrates the efficacy with which the companies deploy their assets. The analysis of profitability ratios demonstrated that Pegasus Airlines exhibited higher and more stable profitability ratios than Turkish Airlines. This indicates that Pegasus is more proficient in cost management and is in a more advantageous position with regard to investment. In general, it has been observed that the financial performance of airline companies is affected by the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic and other economic fluctuations. It can be posited that these companies should reinforce their financial structures, enhance their liquidity positions and develop efficacious cost management strategies in order to guarantee their financial sustainability in the future.

Our findings show that the pandemic had negative effects on airline companies' liquidity, profitability and operational efficiency ratios. In particular, studies such as Keleş and Özulucan (2020) and Beyazgül et al. (2022) show similar findings that companies' financial structures weakened and operational efficiency decreased during the pandemic. It was concluded that Pegasus Airlines was more resilient during the pandemic thanks to its low-cost business model. This finding is in line with the findings of studies such as Asker (2023) and Kızıl and Aslan (2019) regarding the superiority of low-cost business models in crisis periods.

In this study, it is stated that Turkish Airlines (THY) showed resilience during the crisis thanks to its strong financial structure before the pandemic. However, this finding contrasts with the findings of studies such as Koç (2022) that Turkish Airlines needed more external support in terms of crisis management. Our study examines the long-term effects of the pandemic by covering the data range of 2018-2023. In this respect, it differs from short-term studies such as Pehlivanlı (2020), which focus only on the pandemic period.

The study is limited to financial data only for the period 2018-2023. This may limit the long-term analysis of the effects of the pandemic. Examining only two airlines (Turkish Airlines and Pegasus) may reduce the generalizability of the findings. The ratio analysis method focuses on quantitative aspects of financial performance, while qualitative factors (e.g. management decisions, government support) are excluded. The scope of the research can be expanded and more airlines and sectors in different geographies can be analyzed comparatively. 2024 and beyond can be analyzed with more up-to-date data. Detailed financial performance assessments can be made using methods such as Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), Multi-Criteria Decision Making (TOPSIS) and Malmquist Productivity Index. Sustainability strategies of the sector can be analyzed along with their impact on financial performance. The resilience of low-cost airlines and companies with traditional business models against crises can be analyzed in detail. The effects of innovative management strategies on financial results can be analyzed.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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